

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

France's alternative protein research ecosystem

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

276 publications

#7 in publication volume in Europe
+185% from 2020 to 2025

1010 patents

#3 in published patent volume in Europe

Leading research organisations

Unique publications

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

If France makes alternative proteins a strategic priority, the sector could contribute significantly to the national economy by 2040.

€18B

annual economic contribution

+64,000

jobs supported